

Republic of the Philippines
LYCEUM-NORTHWESTERN UNIVERSITY
Francisco Q. Duque Medical Foundation
College of Medicine
Dagupan City, Philippines

**SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE AND FETOMATERNAL OUTCOMES
OF PREGNANT PATIENTS WITH ABRUPTIO PLACENTA FROM
JANUARY 2021 TO MAY 2021 IN REGION I MEDICAL CENTER,
DAGUPAN CITY, PANGASINAN**

A Research Presented
to the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology
Region I Medical Center

In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements
for Clinical Obstetrics Clerkship Rotation

Presented by:

DONA, JAEMYRLEE
DASARI, SREE HARSA
DEVIREDDY, SUSHANTH REDDY

Research Adviser:

Dr. Holly Mae Tandoc

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TITLE.....	1
TABLE OF CONTENTS	2
LIST OF TABLES.....	3
LIST OF FIGURES	4
ABSTRACT	5
CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION.....	6
a. Background of the Study	6
b. Objectives of the Study.....	7
c. Conceptual Framework.....	9
d. Statement of the Problem	8
e. Significance of the Study	10
f. Scope and Limitation of the Study.....	10
CHAPTER II: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE.....	11
CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY.....	13
a. Research Design	13
b. Location	13
c. Population	13
d. Inclusion criteria	13
b. Exclusion criteria.....	13
c. Sample Design	13
d. Data Gathering Procedure.....	14
CHAPTER IV: PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA.....	15
CHAPTER V: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	19
BIBLIOGRAPHY	20
APPENDIX	21
a. Sociodemographic Profile	21

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Table	Page
1	Age of the patients.....	15
2	Gravidity of patients.....	15
3	Marital status.....	16
4	Age of gestation.....	16
5	Mode of delivery.....	16
6	Comorbidities	17
7	Maternal outcome	17
8	Fetal outcome	18
9	Birth weight	18

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure No.	Figure	Page
1	Research Paradigm.....	7

**SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE AND FETOMATERNAL OUTCOMES OF PREGNANT
PATIENTS WITH ABRUPTIO PLACENTA FROM JANUARY 2021 TO MAY 2021 IN REGION
I MEDICAL CENTER, DAGUPAN CITY, PANGASINAN**

Jaemyrlee L. Dona, Sree Harsa Dasari, Sushanth Reddy Devireddy
College of Medicine, Lyceum-Northwestern University, Dagupan City, Pangasinan

ABSTRACT

Objectives: The study aims to determine the sociodemographic profile and fetomaternal outcomes of pregnant patients with abruptio placenta and to determine the frequency of documented cases associated with preeclampsia, postpartum hemorrhage and need for blood products to promote awareness among patients and develop preventive measures in reducing the incidence of adverse outcomes.

Methods: A retrospective study was focused on pregnant women with abruptio placenta admitted in Region 1 Medical Center (R1MC) Dagupan City, Pangasinan from January 2021 to May 2021. Descriptive statistics was used to tally and analyze the various sociodemographic variables.

Results: Fourteen cases met the criteria. Majority of the women involved in the study are aged 21-30 years old (50.00%), gravidity is primigravid (57.14%), single (71.43%), gestational age at delivery tends to be equal in preterm and term (50.00% preterm: 50.00% term), the mode of delivery is via cesarean section (85.71%) and alive (92.86%). Neonates born to women with abruptio placenta have 1500 – 2499 grams birth weight (57.14%) and neonatal outcome of majority is alive (71.43%). The associated incidence with preeclampsia (42.86%) is more than that of postpartum hemorrhage (14.29%) as well as need for blood product or transfusion (7.14%).

Conclusion: Overall, findings revealed that most of the patients with abruptio placenta are in the age group of 21-30 years old, primigravid and single. Fetal outcomes include 1500 – 2499 grams birth weight, preterm and term are equal in numbers, status at birth is alive and delivered via CS. The most commonly associated incidence with abruptio placenta is preeclampsia.

Keywords: abruptio placenta, fetomaternal, preeclampsia, postpartum haemorrhage, primigravid

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Abruptio placenta, also called placental abruption (PA), is the early separation of a placenta from the lining of the uterus before completion of the second stage of labor (Schmidt, et al., 2020). It occurs in about 0.38–1 % of singleton births, and the incidence increases from 1 to 2% among twin pregnancies. It is a major obstetric complication associated with an increased risk of fetal and maternal morbidity and mortality globally, especially in developing countries where the incidence varies from 4 to 6% (Macheku, et al., 2015). Abruptio placenta accounts for 20–25% of antepartum hemorrhage, resulting in increased maternal peripartum risk factors like disseminated intravascular coagulopathy, postpartum hemorrhage (PPH), severe maternal shock, emergency hysterectomy, acute renal failure and maternal death (Saqib, et al., 2020).

Placental abruption occurs when the maternal vessels tear away from the placenta and bleeding occurs between the uterine lining and the maternal side of the placenta. As the blood accumulates, it pushes the uterine wall and placenta apart. The placenta is the fetus' source of oxygen and nutrients as well as the way the fetus excretes waste products. Diffusion to and from the maternal circulatory system is essential to maintaining these life-sustaining functions of the placenta. When accumulating blood causes separation of the placenta from the maternal vascular network, these vital functions of the placenta are interrupted. If the fetus does not receive enough oxygen and nutrients, it dies (Schmidt, et al., 2020)

Preterm detachment of the placenta is potentially disastrous, especially for the fetus, with perinatal mortality of 25 %. The incidence of abruptio placenta is highest at 24–26 weeks of gestation and decreases with advancing gestation (Wielgos, et al., 2017). Adverse fetal outcomes like intrauterine growth restriction, preterm birth, low birth weight, fetal distress, low Apgar score,

transfer to neonatal intensive care unit, stillbirth, congenital anomalies and perinatal death ranging from 4.4 to 67.3% are also observed in cases of abruptio placenta (Saquib, et al., 2020).

Although abruptio placenta occurrence is often unpredictable, Anderson, et al., (2020) stated the potential risk factors included are maternal age category, parity, BMI category, smoking status, deprivation status, marital status, gestational diabetes, gestational hypertension, pre-eclampsia, threatened miscarriage, antepartum hemorrhage (APH) of unknown origin, placenta previa, maternal anemia, premature rupture of membranes (PROM) and gender of the baby.

According to Abirami and Narmadhapriya (2020), the classification of placental abruption is based on the following clinical findings:

Class 0 – asymptomatic:

- Discovery of a blood clot on the maternal side of a delivered placenta

Class 1 – mild

- No sign of vaginal bleeding or a small amount of vaginal bleeding
- Slight uterine tenderness
- Maternal blood pressure and heart rate within normal limits
- No signs of fetal distress

Class 2 – moderate

- No sign of vaginal bleeding to moderate amount of vaginal bleeding
- Significant uterine tenderness with tetanic contractions
- Change in vital signs: maternal tachycardia, orthostatic changes in blood pressure
- Evidence of fetal distress. Clotting profile alteration: hypofibrinogenemia

Class 3 – severe (28 % of all cases); the characteristics include the following:

- No sign of vaginal bleeding to heavy vaginal bleeding
- Tetanic uterus/ board-like consistency on palpation
- Maternal shock

- Clotting profile alteration: hypofibrinogenemia and coagulopathy.
- Fetal death

Objectives of the Study

In general, the objective of this study is to identify the sociodemographic profile of patients with abruptio placenta based on January 2021 to May 2021.

Specifically, this study aims to:

1. To determine the demographic profile of patients with abruptio placenta as to their age, gravidity, age of gestation, mode of delivery and maternal outcomes.
2. To identify the profile of neonate born to women with abruptio placenta in terms of birth weight and neonatal outcomes.
3. To determine the frequency of documented cases of abruptio placenta associated with preeclampsia, postpartum hemorrhage and need for blood products.

Conceptual Framework

This part shows the paradigm of the study, indicating the relationships of the variables with each other. The study used the Input-Process-Output paradigm. See flowchart below.

Statement of the Problem

This study sought to determine the sociodemographic profile of patients with abruptio placenta in Region I Medical Center Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology (R1MC – OBGYN) from January 2021 to May 2021.

Specifically, the study attempted to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the patients as to:
 - a. age;
 - b. gravidity;
 - c. marital status;
 - d. age of gestation;
 - e. mode of delivery;
 - f. maternal outcomes?
2. What is the profile of neonate born to women with abruptio placenta in terms of
 - a. fetal outcomes;
 - b. birth weight?
3. What is the frequency of incidence of abruptio placenta associated with preeclampsia, postpartum hemorrhage and need for blood products?

Significance of the Study

To the Medicine students. This research will help them familiarize the presenting features, manifestations, risk factors and complications of abruptio placenta. Furthermore, this study will serve as guide in knowing the proper approach of different presentations of abruptio placenta.

To the Region I Medical Center – Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology. The findings would help them to monitor the trend of abruptio placenta in the institution as to its incidence, characteristics and outcomes. These can aid them on what to maintain or improve on their strategy and approach to patients with abruptio placenta.

To the Pregnant Population. This study will provide them mindfulness about the causes, risk factors, and several outcomes and consequences of abruptio placenta that can affect their health and life in general.

To Future Researchers. This will serve as reference and guide for the future researchers which aim to make a study related to abruptio placenta and to those who plan to expand studies about this.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study was emphasized on merely assessing the sociodemographic profile along with the maternal and neonatal outcomes of patients with abruptio placenta in R1MC from January 2021 to May 2021. Hence for future similar researches, the scope of data can be extended by including the past years of the admissions in R1MC, and/or can include more data from other tertiary hospitals in Pangasinan to see further comparisons and differences that could affect the results of the study.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Abruptio placenta complicates approximately 2 to 10 per 1000 births (Ananth, et al., 2021). However, as stated by Wielgos, et al., (2017), there is no intervention has been shown to prevent these circumstances. The only management which may reduce the incidence of abruptio placenta is modification of the risk factors. The condition of the fetus should be considered almost simultaneously.

With that being said, in the study of Macheke and co-authors (2015), they stated that the risk factors for abruptio placenta were chronic hypertension, preeclampsia/eclampsia, previous cesarean delivery or abruptio placenta, poor attendance to antenatal care and high parity. Meanwhile, Anderson, et al., (2020) stated that maternal smoking, body mass index (BMI) and fetal gender were not associated with abruptio placenta.

Cesarean section (CS) was the mode of delivery in 78% of abruption cases, 33% had postpartum hemorrhage and 20% had received blood products. Adverse fetal outcomes were as follows: 51% of the cases had preterm delivery, 47% of the babies had a birth weight of less than 2.5 kg (Saquib, et al., 2020) while stillbirths were 30.2% (Sengodan and Dhanapal 2017).

As Li, et al., (2019) mentioned, abdominal pain (68%) and bleeding (35%) comprise the classical symptoms of placental abruption but the clinical picture varies from asymptomatic, in which the diagnosis is made by inspection of the placenta at delivery, to massive abruption leading to fetal death and severe maternal morbidity. Wielgos, et al., (2017) added that during the examination, the uterus may be disproportionately enlarged and an increased tonicity is often present. Moreover, rapid, painful contractions which follow one another can occur. Placental abruption results in fetal distress. Altered fetal activity is one of the most alarming signs. The patient may present with decreased or absent fetal movements.

The diagnosis of placental abruption should consider risk factors, symptoms, physical signs, dynamic ultrasound monitoring, and cardiac care (Li, et al., 2019). The most useful mechanism for recognizing the onset of placental abruption is an assessment of the patient. The physical examination includes palpation of the uterus (Schmidt, et al., 2020)

Abruptio placenta is one of the obstetric emergency which results in maternal morbidity and fetal mortality. A timely referral, early identification of risk factors, early diagnosis, can improve the maternal outcome and fetal outcome (Abirami and Narmadhapriya, 2020).

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

Research design

A retrospective study was done in Region 1 Medical Center. Daily admission census from the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology were reviewed. The study includes obstetric patients admitted from January 2021 to May 2021 who were diagnosed with abruptio placenta. Sociodemographic profile of patients was extracted and tallied according to age, gravidity, marital status, and age of gestation, mode of delivery and comorbidities on final diagnosis. Results of the study were compared and interpreted.

Location

The study was conducted in Region 1 Medical Center Obstetrics and Gynecology Department in Dagupan City, Pangasinan

Population

Patients admitted at Obstetrics and Gynecology Department with diagnosis of abruptio placenta at Region 1 Medical Center from January 2021 to May 2021.

Inclusion criteria

All patients who have been admitted with diagnosis of abruptio placenta at Region 1 Medical Center Obstetrics and Gynecology Department from January to May 2021.

Exclusion criteria

We excluded those patients who were not diagnosed with abruptio placenta.

Sampling design

The study design is a retrospective study and will be utilizing the daily census of patients who are diagnosed with abruptio placenta at Region 1 Medical Center from January 2021 to May 2021.

Data gathering procedure

The researchers asked a copy of the daily census from the Obstetrics and Gynecology Department. Data collection commenced after the researchers received the daily census.

Sociodemographic features will be recorded and categorized:

1. Maternal age
2. Gravidity
3. Marital status
4. Age of gestation
5. Mode of delivery
6. Maternal outcomes
7. Fetal outcomes
8. Birth weight

CHAPTER 4

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This section presents the statistical results, analysis, and interpretation of the sociodemographic profile of patients with abruptio placenta.

I. Sociodemographic Profile

A. Age

TABLE 1
Age of the patients

Age	Frequency	Percent
≤20 years old	2	14.29%
21 - 30 years old	7	50.00%
31 - 40 years old	4	28.57%
≥41	1	7.14%
Total	14	100%

For the age of patients admitted with abruptio placenta 2 (14.29%) are ≤20, 7 (50%) and 4 (28.57%) are between the age group of 21-30 and 31-40 respectively. However only 1 (7.14%) belongs to the age group ≥41 years.

B. Gravidity

TABLE 2
Gravidity of the patients

Gravidity	Frequency	Percent
Primigravid	8	57.14%
Multigravid	3	21.43%
Grand multigravid	3	21.43%
Total	14	100%

For the gravidity of the patients, 8 (71.43%) are primigravid, 3 (21.43%) are multigravid and 3 (21.43%) are grand multigravid.

C. Marital Status

TABLE 3
Marital status of the patients

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
Single	10	71.43%
Married	4	28.57%
Total	14	100.00%

There are about 10 (71.43%) singles whereas 4 (28.57%) are married.

D. Age of gestation

TABLE 4
Age of gestation of the patients

Age of gestation	Frequency	Percent
Preterm	7	50.00%
Term	7	50.00%
Post-term	0	0.00 %
Total	14	100.0 %

There are about 7 (50%) both in preterm and term. There are no post term deliveries.

E. Mode of delivery

TABLE 5
Mode of delivery of the patients

Mode of delivery	Frequency	Percent
NSVD	2	14.29%
CS	12	85.71%
Total	14	100.0 %

For the mode of delivery, 2 (14.29%) patients delivered by normal spontaneous vaginal delivery (NSVD) and the rest 12 (85.71%) were delivered by cesarean section (CS).

F. Comorbidities

TABLE 6
Comorbidities of the patients

Comorbidities	Frequency	Percent
Preeclampsia	6	42.86%
Post-partum hemorrhage	2	14.29%
Need for blood transfusion	1	7.14%
No comorbidities	5	35.71%
Total	14	100.00%

Preeclampsia is the most common comorbidity associated with abruptio placenta which comprises of 42.86% of the total cases, whereas postpartum hemorrhage is the comorbidity in 14.29% of the abruptio placenta cases. Of the total cases, 7.14% required blood transfusion as per our study in R1MC in the time span of 5 months from January to May 2021.

II. Maternal Outcome

TABLE 7
Maternal outcome of the patients

Maternal outcome	Frequency	Percent
Live	13	92.86%
Deceased	1	7.14%
Total	14	100.00%

For the maternal outcome, 13 (92.86%) are alive and 1 (7.14%) has deceased.

III. Fetal

A. Fetal Outcome

TABLE 8
Fetal outcome

Fetal outcome	Frequency	Percent
Alive	10	71.43%
Stillbirth	4	28.57%
Total	14	100.00%

For the fetal outcome, 10 (71.43%) are live births and 4 (28.57%) are stillbirths.

B. Birth weight

TABLE 9
Birth weight

Birth weight	Frequency	Percent
<1500 grams	1	7.14%
1500 – 2499 grams	8	57.14%
2500 – 4000 grams	5	35.71%
>4000 grams	0	0.00%
Total	14	100.00%

For the birth weight (Rao, et al., 2018), 8 (57.14%) of the neonates have 1500 – 2499 grams which corresponds to moderately low birth weight. Five (35.71%) were recorded to have normal birth weight that is ranging from 2500 – 4000 grams, and 1(7.14%) neonate has very low birth weight having only <1500 grams.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Majority of the patients with abruptio placenta are in the age group of 21-30 years old, primigravid and single. Most of the deliveries of abruptio placenta is via CS and frequency of preterm and term numbers are almost the same with more live births than still births. Most of the neonates born to placental abruption mothers have 1500 – 2499 grams birth weight.

The associated incidence with preeclampsia is more than that of postpartum hemorrhage as well as need for blood product or transfusion.

Recommendation

The following recommendation are drawn from our study:

1. In evaluation of fetomaternal outcomes, the researchers recommend to further correlate it with the variables such as age, gravidity, marital status, age of gestation, mode of delivery and comorbidities especially preeclampsia, post-partum hemorrhage and the need for blood transfusion to find out if there are differences in the outcomes depending on whether or not they have been exposed to any factors of interest.
2. The survey and research on abruptio placenta risk factors and associated complication must be expanded and update. This further provides information regarding other maternal and neonatal outcomes which may have existed but were not part of the study.
3. Proper awareness should be provided among the people in communities on the incidence and outcome of abruptio placenta.
4. The research is limited with few profiles and can be extended on more sociodemographic variables. This study is limited to R1MC and can be expanded to larger area and population.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Ananth CV, et al. Placental abruption: Pathophysiology, clinical features, diagnosis and consequences. <https://www.uptodate.com/contents/search>. Accessed June3, 2021.
- Anderson E, Raja EA, Shetty A, Gissler M, Gatt M, Bhattacharya S, et al. (2020) Changing risk factors for placental abruption: A case crossover study using routinely collected data from Finland, Malta and Aberdeen. *PLoS ONE* 15(6): e0233641.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0233641>
- Li, Y., Tian, Y., Liu, N., Chen, Y., & Wu, F. (2019). Analysis of 62 placental abruption cases: Risk factors and clinical outcomes. *Taiwanese Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 58(2), 223-226. doi:10.1016/j.tjog.2019.01.010
- Og, D. K. (2020). Abruptio Placenta – A Study in Tertiary Care Centre. *Journal of Medical Science And Clinical Research*, 08(01). doi:10.18535/jmscr/v8i1.132
- Rao, Jiaming, et al. “Trend and Risk Factors of Low Birth Weight and Macrosomia in South China, 2005–2017: a Retrospective Observational Study.” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2018, doi:10.1038/s41598-018-21771-6.
- Saqib, S., Hamza, L., Alsayed, A., Saeed, F., & Abbas, M. (2020). Prevalence and Its Feto-Maternal Outcome in Placental Abruption: A Retrospective Study for 5 Years from Dubai Hospital. *Dubai Medical Journal*, 3(1), 26-31. doi:10.1159/000506256
- Sengodan SS, Dhanapal M. Abruptio placenta: a retrospective study on maternal and perinatal outcome. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol* 2017;6:4389-92
- Schmidt P, Skelly CL, Raines DA. Placental Abruption. [Updated 2020 Jul 5]. *In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2021 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK482335/>*
- Wielgos, M., Jarmuzek, P., & Pietrzak, B. (2017). Abruptio Placenta. *Management and Therapy of Late Pregnancy Complications*, 37-52. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-48732-8_3

APPENDIX

NO	Age/ Status	Education	Admitting Diagnosis	Final diagnosis	Intervention
1	34/S	HS	G1P0 Pregnancy uterine 37 5/7 weeks AOG, cephalic in beginning labor, GDM controlled, t/c abruptio placenta, NRFS	G1P1 (1001) Pregnancy uterine term cephalic livebirth delivered via LTCS I under SAB for NRFS (persistent fetal tachycardia) baby boy, BW 3150 grams, BL 51 cm, AS 8/9, BS 39 weeks AGA; GDM controlled, Pelvic endometriosis, Myoma Uteri	LTCS I
2	27/S	COLLEGE UNDERGRADUATE	G1P0 Pregnancy uterine 39 weeks AOG, not in labor, Preeclampsia with severe features	G1P1 (1001) Pregnancy uterine term cephalic livebirth delivered via LTCS I under SAB for abruptio placenta, baby boy, BW 1920 grams, BL 44 cm, AS 7/9, BS 38 weeks SGA, Abruptio Placenta, Preeclampsia with severe features	LTCS I
3	25/S	HS	G3P1 (1011) Pregnancy uterine 39 2/7 weeks AOG, cephalic in beginning labor, gestational hypertension	G3P2 (2012) Pregnancy uterine term cephalic delivered via LTCS I with IUD under SAB for NRFS (fetal bradycardia) a live baby boy BW 2295 g BL 49 cm AS 7, 9 BS 39 weeks, AGA, preeclampsia with severe features, beginning abruptio placenta	LTCS I with IUD

4	27/S	HS	G2P1 (1001) Pregnancy uterine 33 2/7 weeks AOG, cephalic in preterm labor, twin gestation, anemia probably secondary to abruptio placenta, r/o HELLP syndrome, t/c IUFD	G2P2 (1201) Pregnancy uterine preterm stillborn delivered vaginally a set of twins: twin A baby boy BW 1845 g; twin B baby boy BW 1805 g, hypovolemic shock secondary to acute blood loss secondary to abruptio placenta, HELLP syndrome	NSVD
5	19/S	SENIOR HS	G1P0 Pregnancy uterine 40 4/7 weeks AOG, cephalic in beginning labor; Premature rupture of membranes x 10 hours	G1P1 (1001) Pregnancy uterine term cephalic livebirth delivered via LTCS I under GETA for NRFS (fetal bradycardia) baby girl, BW 2610 grams, BL 49 cm, AS 8/9, BS 38 weeks AGA; PROM, Beginning abruptio placenta	LTCS I
6	33/M	HS	G5P4 (4004) Pregnancy uterine 36 5/7 weeks AOG. Cephalic in preterm labor, abruptio placenta	G5P5 (5005) Pregnancy uterine term cephalic delivered via LTCS 1 under SAB for abruptio placenta a live baby girl BW 2790g BL 45cm AS 6,9 BS 38 weeks AGA, Abruptio Placenta, Grandmultiparity, FPA (BTL)	LTCS 1 with BTL
7	14/S	ELEMENTARY	G1P0 Pregnancy uterine 35 2/7 weeks AOG, cephalic in preterm labor; Eclampsia t/c abruptio placenta; Teenage pregnancy	G1P1 (1001) Pregnancy uterine, term, cephalic, delivered via LTCS I under GETA for eclampsia to a live baby boy, BW: 2,770 grams, BL: 53 cms, AS: 5,6,7, BS: 37 weeks AGA; Beginning abruptio placenta; Teenage	LTCS 1

				pregnancy; Community acquired pneumonia	
8	41/M	HS	G7P6 (6006) Pregnancy uterine 38 4/7 weeks AOG, cephalic in beginning labor, Prelabor rupture of membrane, Pre-eclampsia with severe features, abruptio placenta	G7P7 (7007) Pregnancy uterine term cephalic delivered via LTCS 1 with BTL for abruptio placenta, a live baby boy BW 2765g BL 50cm AS 8,9 BS 37 weeks AGA, Prelabor rupture of membrane, Pre-eclampsia with severe features, abruptio placenta, Grandmultiparity, FPA (BTL)	LTCS 1 with BTL
9	27/S	HS	G1P0 Pregnancy uterine 32 weeks AOG, cephalic in beginning labor; Preeclampsia with severe features t/c abruptio placenta	G1P1 (0101) Pregnancy uterine preterm cephalic livebirth delivered via LTCS I under SAB for preeclampsia with severe features, baby boy, BW 1630 grams, BL 30 cm, AS 2/2, BS 32 weeks AGA; Multiple congenital anomaly (t/c TORCH syndrome) Preeclampsia with severe features	LTCS 1
10	27/S	COLLEGE GRADUATED	G1P0 Pregnancy uterine 33 3/7 weeks AOG, frank breech in preterm labor, Abruptio Placenta, Anemia secondary to acute blood loss	G1P1 (0100) Pregnancy uterine preterm frank breech delivered via LTCS I under GETA for abruptio placenta, baby girl, BW 1950 grams; Abruptio Placenta, Anemia secondary to acute blood loss	LTCS I, Blood transfusion

11	22/S	HS	G1P0 Pregnancy uterine 31 weeks AOG, cephalic in preterm labor; Preeclampsia with severe features; Abruptio placenta; Intrauterine fetal demise	G1P1 (0100) Pregnancy uterine, preterm, cephalic, stillbirth, delivered via LTCS I under SAB for Abruptio placenta, baby girl, BW: 1,290 grams; Preeclampsia with severe features, controlled; Abruptio placenta; Intrauterine fetal demise; Urinary tract infection; Hypokalemia, mild	LTCS 1
12	31/M	HS	G2P1 (1001) pregnancy uterine 34 4/7 weeks AOG cephalic in labor; eclampsia	G2P2 (1102) pregnancy uterine preterm cephalic delivered via LTCS I under SAB for Eclampsia a live baby girl, BW 1700g, BL 50cm, AS 5/9 BS 34weeks AGA, Eclampsia; Beginning Abruptio placenta; family planning acceptor IUD	LTCS I with IUD
13	39/M	HS	G6P3 (3023) PU preterm by size CIPTL; CHVD with superimposed preeclampsia; T/c abruptio placenta; HELLP syndrome	G6P5 (3123) PU preterm cephalic stillbirth delivered vaginally a baby BW 1800 grams; CHVD with superimposed preeclampsia; abruptio placenta; HELLP syndrome	NSD followed by curettage
14	22/S	HS	G1P0 Pregnancy uterine 34 3/7 weeks AOG, cephalic in preterm labor, abruptio placenta	G1P1 (1001) Pregnancy uterine, preterm, cephalic, delivered via LTCS 1 to a live Baby girl, BW: 1,880 grams, BL: 43 cms, AS: 8,9, BS: 35 weeks AGA; hypoxic encephalopathy secondary to abruptio placenta	LTCS 1 WITH IUD